

Enhanced Optoelectronic Behaviour of Potassium-Doped CdS Thin Films: Effect of Doping Concentration

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Abstract

In this study, the structural, morphological, optical, and electrical properties of potassium (K)-doped cadmium sulfide (CdS) thin films were systematically investigated. Undoped CdS thin films were initially deposited on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates via the chemical bath deposition (CBD) method and served as reference samples. Potassium doping was achieved by incorporating potassium chloride (KCl) into the chemical bath at concentrations of 20 mM, 30 mM, 40 mM, and 50 mM. Potassium incorporation, achieved by introducing KCl at varying concentrations, significantly enhanced film homogeneity, crystal quality, and optoelectronic performance. Among the doped samples, K30 exhibited high phase purity and uniform morphology, while K40 displayed a compact structure and increased carrier density. These improvements are expected to minimize recombination losses, reduce current leakage, and enhance charge transport, highlighting the potential of optimally K-doped CdS films for high-efficiency photovoltaic applications.

Keywords: Photovoltaics, alkali treatment, CdS, CBD, KCl salt

1. Introduction

Cadmium sulfide (CdS) has emerged as a key semiconductor material in optoelectronic applications due to its direct band gap of 2.42 eV, high optical absorption coefficient, low production cost, and ease of fabrication via simple deposition techniques (Alexander et al., 2014). CdS thin films are widely used as buffer layers in thin-film solar cells, where fundamental properties such as band gap, crystal structure, crystallite size, and uniformity of surface coverage significantly influence overall device performance (Kartopu et al., 2014). CdS thin films can be synthesized using various deposition techniques including chemical spray pyrolysis, spray coating, electrochemical deposition, and chemical bath deposition (CBD) (Plotnikov et al., 2008). The choice of deposition method depends largely on the intended application of the CdS semiconductor layer. Additionally, whether alkali metal doping will be applied plays a critical role in the selection of the fabrication technique. For instance, some methods (e.g., spray coating) may be less economically favourable due to high equipment costs. Among these, CBD is a low-cost and straightforward technique capable of producing compact, smooth, and stable films at relatively low temperatures with good control over film properties. In this study, the CBD method was employed to fabricate K-doped CdS thin films. In recent years, extensive research on CIGSe ($\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})\text{Se}_2$)-based solar cells has focused on the effects of alkali metal incorporation into absorber layers and their influence on overall device performance. Sodium (Na) was the first alkali metal reported to enhance the performance of CIGSe absorbers, and it remains the most extensively studied. This effect was initially discovered in the 1990s when a research group inadvertently used a substrate containing sodium. Subsequent investigations revealed that alkali metals tend to accumulate at grain boundaries in CIGSe absorber layers, contributing to improved charge carrier lifetimes and higher device efficiencies (Laemmle et al., 2014). Moreover, when heavy alkali metals (e.g., K, Rb, Cs) were co-introduced into Na-containing

absorbers, partial substitution of Na at grain boundaries was observed, leading to better grain boundary passivation (Reinhard et al., 2015). Therefore, the observed efficiency enhancements have been partially attributed to improved structural quality and defect passivation of the absorber layer. The highest reported efficiencies to date have been achieved using Rb (22.6%) and Cs (23.35%) doping (Jackson et al., 2016; Nakamura et al., 2019). In contrast, there is a limited number of studies in the literature concerning potassium-doped CdS thin films. In this study, CdS thin films with various K doping concentrations were synthesized via the CBD method and systematically analyzed to investigate the effects of potassium incorporation on the structural and optoelectronic properties of the films.

2. Material and Methods

In this work, as a substrate, FTO-coated glass (Surface resistivity $10\Omega/\text{sq}$, Solaronix) was used (Figure 1). Cadmium acetate dehydrates ($\text{Cd}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Thiourea (H_2NCSNH_2) solution as a sulphur source, and alkali metal salt KCl were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (chemicals company). In thin film deposition techniques, the substrate plays a crucial role, as it directly influences the quality and structural properties of the resulting film. Therefore, the morphological and structural characteristics of the substrate must be thoroughly investigated, since they can significantly affect the growth behaviour and overall performance of the deposited layer. In Figure 1 presents the SEM image of the FTO (Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide) substrate used in this study. As seen in the image, the surface of the FTO substrate consists of granular structures with sizes ranging approximately from 100 nm to 500 nm. These granules exhibit a rough and irregular morphology, which is believed to contribute to an increased surface area—a favourable attribute in thin film applications. Moreover, since both undoped and alkali-doped CdS thin films will be grown on this morphology, the surface characteristics of the substrate are of particular importance. Accordingly, detailed SEM analysis is

essential for understanding the impact of the substrate's morphology on subsequent film growth. As shown in Fig.1, the XRD diffraction pattern of the FTO substrate displays sharp and intense characteristic peaks

corresponding to the substrate at Bragg angles of 26.6°, 33.8°, 37.85°, 38.9°, 42.55°, 51.65° (the most intense), and 54.75°. These peaks are marked with asterisks, as the same substrate structure will be used in subsequent analyses.

Figure 1. SEM image and XRD diffraction pattern of FTO substrate

This study, CdS thin films were deposited via the conventional chemical bath deposition (CBD) method. To fabricate CdS:Alk thin films on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates, potassium chloride (KCl) salt was introduced into the chemical bath as an additive to the standard CBD process (Figure 2). Prior to deposition, a rigorous cleaning procedure was applied to the substrates to eliminate any surface contamination that could adversely affect film morphology and quality. Accordingly, the FTO substrates were ultrasonically cleaned for 10 minutes in each of the following solvents: 2-propanol, methanol, and deionized water. The cleaned substrates were then dried using a nitrogen gas stream and prepared for deposition. The deposition process was carried out in two stages. In the first stage, cadmium and sulphur precursor solutions were prepared to obtain undoped CdS films. The cadmium solution was obtained by dissolving 0.44 grams of cadmium salt in deionized water to a total volume of 100 ml. Similarly, thiourea, used as the sulphur source, was dissolved in 100 ml of deionized water. In the second stage, a chemical bath was prepared in a double-walled

beaker mounted on a magnetic stirrer. The beaker was connected to a thermostatic water bath to maintain a constant temperature. The bath was composed of 50 ml ultra-pure water, 11.25 ml cadmium solution, 30 ml thiourea solution, and 58.75 ml ultra-pure water. The cleaned substrates were suspended vertically in the bath, and the temperature was maintained at 60 °C by circulating hot water through the outer wall of the beaker using the thermostatic bath. Once turbidity was observed, the deposition was continued for 15 minutes. The double-walled beaker ensured stable and homogeneous temperature distribution throughout the deposition process. After deposition, the samples were removed from the bath, rinsed thoroughly with deionized water to remove residuals, and dried under a stream of nitrogen gas. For the fabrication of alkali-doped CdS:Alk films, KCl salt was added to the 58.75 ml portion of ultra-pure water in accordance with the desired molarity. To investigate the influence of alkali metal incorporation on CdS films, KCl was added to the chemical bath at concentrations of 20 mM, 30 mM, 40 mM, and 50 mM, resulting in the formation of CdS:Alk thin films with varying

alkali doping levels (Figure 3). These concentrations were obtained through experimental testing for our procedure. The addition of 10 mM K did not provide

improvements in CdS, and since more degradation occurred at 60 mM, this range, where improvements were observed in different areas, was used.

Figure 2. CBD setup and sample illustration

Figure 3. Characteristic times of chemical bath and the CdS films coated using different amounts of alkali metal

3. Sample Characterization

The structural properties and phase purity of CdS films were studied by x-ray diffraction (XRD) and Rietveld refinement technique using (Panalytical X'pert Highscore Plus). For structural refinement, high-resolution grazing incidence x-ray diffraction (GIXRD) data were recorded with a step size of 0.02° and at 0.4° grazing angle (using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$, MP-XRD Panalytical-Empyrean). The surface morphology of the films and elemental compositions were investigated by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-ESEM-EDS, FEI Quanta 450 FEG). Film thicknesses were determined from the cross-

sectional FESEM images ((FE-ESEM-EDS, FEI Quanta 450 FEG). Ultraviolet–visible (UV-visible) spectroscopy was used to calculate the optical band gap of the films (Hach Lange UV DR 5000). Electrical properties of the films were studied using Hall measurements (HLF 1.3).

4. Discussion

4.1. XRD results

Mineralogical and textural analyses provide critical insights into mineral identification, the differentiation between diagenetic and detrital phases, quantitative abundances of minerals, The CdS is a binary semiconductor belonging

to the II–VI group. It can crystallize in either hexagonal or cubic phases. When CdS exhibits a hexagonal structure, the reported lattice parameters are $a = 4.137 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.716 \text{ \AA}$, whereas for the cubic phase, the lattice parameter is $a = 5.825 \text{ \AA}$ (Adachi, 2004). Among these, the hexagonal crystal structure is reported to be the most observed form (Madelung et al., 1999). The XRD spectra of both undoped and potassium-doped CdS thin films are presented in Figure 4. The XRD peaks corresponding to the FTO substrate are marked with asterisks. As observed from the diffraction patterns, the peaks indexed to the (100), (002), (101), (110), and (112) planes represent the hexagonal phase (ICDD No: 62-0323), while the (111) and (220) peaks correspond to the cubic phase (ICDD No: 02-9278). Overall, the spectra in the 2θ range of 20° - 60° indicate that the CdS thin films exhibit a mixed phase structure, consisting of

$$D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta \quad (1)$$

Here, K is the Scherrer constant (typically taken as 0.9 for spherical crystallites), λ is the wavelength of the incident X-ray radiation (1.5406 \AA), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the selected diffraction peak, and

$$2d\sin\theta = n\lambda \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon = \beta\cos\theta/4 \quad (3)$$

$$\delta = 1/D^2 \quad (4)$$

In this study, GI-XRD (Grazing Incidence X-Ray Diffraction) measurements were conducted using consistent measurement parameters for all samples. One of the primary reasons for employing this technique is to minimize the diffraction signal contribution from the substrate as much as possible. Accordingly, the incident angle (ω) between the sample and the X-ray beam was set to 0.4° , the scan range was selected from 20° to 60° , and the step size for data acquisition was 0.05° . The obtained diffraction patterns were analysed using Rietveld refinement in the High Score Plus software. Considering the

both cubic and hexagonal phases, with the proportions varying depending on the level of potassium doping. To further investigate the effects of potassium doping on the crystallographic parameters of CdS thin films, the (110) H and (220) C diffraction peaks located between 42° and 46° were fitted. The θ and β values required for subsequent calculations were extracted from these fitted peaks and are listed in Table 1. As seen in Table 1, while the crystal size increased with the K doping concentration, the d-interplanar distance remained the same. Additionally, stress and dislocation density decreased with increasing K concentration. Additionally, detailed Rietveld refinement results for the crystal structure are provided in Table 2 and Table 3. The average crystallite size was calculated using the Scherrer equation (Hodes, 2002).

θ is the corresponding Bragg angle. Using an appropriate diffraction peak, the interplanar spacing (d), strain (ε), and dislocation density (δ) can be calculated using the following equations:

phase percentages presented in Table 2 and Table 3, it is observed that the hexagonal phase content increases in the CdS:K20 and CdS:K30 films, whereas the cubic phase fraction rises in the CdS:K40 and CdS:K50 films. Furthermore, examining the R Bragg values, which indicate the error margin of the Rietveld analysis, shows that all films except CdS:K20 exhibit lower error values. This result highlights the improved crystallographic quality of the other samples and particularly makes the CdS:K30 sample more suitable for electronic applications due to its higher single-phase content. The incorporation of potassium

(K) ions into the cadmium sulfide (CdS) lattice can alter the phase stability by influencing interatomic bond energies and lattice parameters. Specifically, the relatively large ionic radius and monovalent nature of potassium can induce localized strain within the CdS crystal structure. This strain may favor the formation of the thermodynamically more

stable hexagonal (wurtzite) phase, thereby promoting an increase in the hexagonal phase fraction with increasing potassium concentration. A deeper understanding of these mechanisms could be achieved through further theoretical studies, such as *ab initio* calculations and thermodynamic modeling.

Table 1. 2θ , FWHM values of XRD (110)H and (220)C diffraction peaks of undoped and potassium-doped CdS thin films (CdS:K) and calculated crystal size (D, nm), d-interplanar distance (Å), stress (ϵ , rad) and dislocation density using these values

	2θ (°)	FWHM (°)	D (nm)	d (Å)	ϵ ($\times 10^{-3}$)	d ($\times 10^{-2}$)
CdS	44.33	1.24	7.24	2.042	5.00	1.91
CdS:K20	44.37	1.09	8.23	2.040	4.40	1.48
CdS:K30	44.35	1.07	8.39	2.041	4.32	1.42
CdS:K40	44.34	1.06	8.45	2.041	4.28	1.40
CdS:K50	44.38	0.93	9.66	2.040	3.75	1.07

Table 2. Reitveld results of the hexagonal structure of CdS:K doped samples

	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	Calculated density (g cm^{-3})	Cell volume (10^6)(p)m ³)	R _{Bragg}	%
CdS	4.150	4.150	6.737	4.77	100.480	14.76	-
CdS:K20	4.125	4.125	6.557	4.96	96.628	13.47	99.6
CdS:K30	4.122	4.122	6.823	4.78	100.419	7.40	98.6
CdS:K40	4.130	4.130	7.009	4.73	101.460	10.69	35.2
CdS:K50	4.093	4.093	6.860	4.82	99.513	5.63	31.6

Table 3. Reitveld results of the cubic structure of CdS:K doped samples

	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	Calculated density (g cm^{-3})	Cell volume (106)(p)m3)	R _{Bragg}	%
CdS	5.818	5.818	5.818	4.87	196.93	-	-
CdS:K20	5.875	5.875	5.875	4.73	202.787	0.50	0.4
CdS:K30	5.877	5.877	5.877	4.78	199.470	1.64	1.4
CdS:K40	5.810	5.810	5.810	4.89	199.247	5.56	64.8
CdS:K50	5.823	5.823	5.823	4.86	197.409	3.07	68.4

Figure 4. XRD spectra of undoped and potassium-doped CdS thin films

4.2. SEM results

The Figure 5 presents the surface SEM image of the CdS thin film deposited on the FTO substrate. These images will serve as a reference for the subsequent sections of this study. The CdS thin films shown here were fabricated using the standard chemical bath deposition (CBD) procedure and therefore contain no dopants. As illustrated in Figure 5, although the CdS thin film was deposited compactly and densely onto the FTO substrate using the standard procedure, a limited number of voids and agglomerations were still observed on the surface. These voids and agglomerates are marked on the image with red circles and white arrows, respectively. Such

morphological imperfections are known to negatively impact the performance of electronic and optoelectronic device structures. In particular, the presence of pores or voids in any layer of a multilayered solar cell structure may lead to current leakage and, consequently, a reduction in device efficiency (Fardi et al., 2013; Gretener et al., 2013). Finally, additional characterization analyses were conducted on the undoped CdS thin film, and the obtained results are presented alongside those of potassium-doped CdS films. The purpose of this comparative approach is to provide a clearer understanding of the differences between the undoped and doped CdS thin films.

Figure 5. SEM surface image and EDS plot of CdS thin film deposited on FTO substrate by chemical bath deposition method

The surface SEM images of the potassium-doped CdS sample series (CdS:K) are presented in Figure 6. As seen in the images, the K20 and K50 samples exhibit numerous voids (highlighted with red circles) and agglomerates of various sizes (indicated by white arrows) on their surfaces. In contrast, the K30 and K40 films appear to cover the FTO

substrate in a homogeneous, compact, and dense manner, except for a few minor agglomerates. When compared to the surface morphology of the undoped CdS films, it can be concluded that the addition of 30 mM and 40 mM potassium leads to improvements in the deposition characteristics of CdS thin films on FTO substrates.

Figure 6. Surface SEM images of potassium-doped CdS sample series (CdS:K)

The thicknesses of undoped CdS and potassium-doped CdS thin films (CdS:K) coated on FTO were determined using the cross-sectional views shown in Figure 6. The thickness of sample K20 was found to be approximately the same as the reference sample. At other doping ratios, the thicknesses increased compared to the reference sample.

This increase in thickness without compromising surface homogeneity and compactness can be considered an indication of improved coating reaction mechanism in the chemical bath. Furthermore, considering the reaction turbidity times, the slightly slower reaction rate confirms the information that the

slower reaction rate increases thickness and homogeneity.

4.3. Optical properties

The UV-Vis measurements of the potassium-doped CdS thin films were carried

$$\alpha h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g)^n \quad (5)$$

Here, α represents the absorption coefficient, A is a material-specific constant, h is Planck's constant, and ν is the frequency of the incident light. The exponent n in the Tauc equation is taken as 2 for indirect semiconductors and $\frac{1}{2}$ for direct semiconductors. Since CdS is a direct bandgap semiconductor (Hodes, 2002), $n = \frac{1}{2}$ was used in this study. Based on this equation, the optical band gaps were estimated by plotting the Tauc curve, i.e., a graph of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus

out in the wavelength range of 200–800 nm, and the corresponding Tauc plots were derived from the obtained absorption spectra. The calculations were performed using the Tauc equation.

$h\nu$. The bandgap energy (E_g) was determined by extrapolating the linear portion of the curve and identifying the intercept with the photon energy axis. Figure 7 presents the relevant portion of the Tauc plots in the range of approximately 2.0–3.0 eV. As shown, the effect of potassium doping on the bandgap energy (E_g) appears only partially in the K40 sample. The calculated bandgap values are consistent with the well-known literature value of 2.42 eV for CdS (Hodes, 2002).

Figure 7. Tauc and E_g curves of potassium-doped CdS thin films

4.4. Electrical properties

Finally, Hall effect measurements were performed. The measurements were conducted at room temperature, and the setup was prepared by soldering copper wires to the four corners of each sample to form an active area of approximately 0.8–1 cm². During the

measurements, a magnetic field strength of 0.5 T was applied. The results obtained from the Hall measurements are summarized in Table 4. Based on the data, it can be stated that carrier concentration and electrical conductivity did not change significantly across the samples. However, excluding the CdS:K50 sample, the

intended doping effect was successfully achieved in the other potassium-doped films. A slight increase in carrier concentration was observed in the CdS:K20 and CdS:K30 samples, indicating some improvement in

electrical properties. Notably, the CdS:K40 sample exhibited a clear and substantial increase in carrier concentration. In this sense, it will lead to an increase in the performance of K40 solar cells.

Table 4. Analysis results of HEMS measurements of undoped and potassium-doped CdS thin films (CdS:K)

	Type	σ ($\times 10^{-2}$) ($\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	Hall mobility (μ) ($\text{cm}^2/\text{V.s}$)	Carrier con. (n) ($\times 10^{16}$) (cm^{-3})	Hall coeff. (cm^3/C)	R (Ohm.cm)
CdS	n	15.1	35.89	2.63	237.6	6.59
CdS:K20	n	14.8	34.60	2.67	233.7	6.74
CdS:K30	n	14.79	34.72	2.65	202.6	6.76
CdS:K40	n	14.9	29.89	3.11	200.6	6.71
CdS:K50	n	14.72	39.25	2.34	266.6	6.79

5. Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that potassium (K) doping is an effective strategy for optimizing the structural and optoelectronic properties of cadmium sulfide (CdS) thin films, with significant implications for their performance in solar cell architectures. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses of the K-doped CdS films reveal a direct correlation between increasing potassium concentration and a reduction in structural defects, leading to a larger average crystallite size. This successful structural modification is crucial as it minimizes grain boundaries and other crystalline imperfections that can act as recombination centers for charge carriers, thereby limiting device efficiency. Furthermore, field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) micrographs show that these structural improvements translate into enhanced surface morphology, particularly in the K30 and K40 samples. The K30 sample, for example, exhibits a high degree of hexagonal phase purity (approximately 99%), which is known to be the most desirable crystallographic form for CdS in photovoltaic applications. The K40 sample demonstrates the lowest surface defect density of all investigated samples, indicating a highly uniform and well-formed film surface. The enhanced structural and morphological quality of the K-doped films directly improves their electrical and optical performance.

Specifically, the reduction in structural defects and the increase in crystallite size contribute to an improved electrical conductivity. The K40 sample, in particular, displays a significant increase in carrier concentration, a critical factor for charge transport in the device. In conclusion, the controlled incorporation of potassium into CdS thin films at optimal concentrations, particularly at the K30 and K40 doping levels, yields significant improvements in structural, morphological, electrical, and optical properties. These findings affirm the potential of K-doping as a viable and effective method to improve the performance of CdS-based solar cells, paving the way for more efficient and stable optoelectronic devices.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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